

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

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IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN BOLALAR INTERNAT UYIDA REABILITATSIYA XIZMATI VA HAMSHIRA ISH FAOLIYATI TAHLILI

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Kalit so'zlar: nogiron bolalar, internat uyi, reabilitatsiya, hamshira ish faoliyati

Annotatsiya: Imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar internatida reabilitatsion dastur ta'sir doirasi tahlili, internat tibbiy hamshira ishi faoliyati va unga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni ijtimoiy ahamiyatini o'rganish, hamshira ish faoliyatini ekspert baholash, tibbiy-ijtimoiy xizmatlar muassasadagi tarbiyalanuvchi bolalar (n-451) hayot tarzi, salomatlik ko'rsatkichlari, kasallik tarixi o'rganildi. Hamshiralar (52) tibbiy yordam sifati, tibbiy texnika texnologiyalardan foydalanish darajasi tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot natijasi bo'yicha xulosa va hamshira parvarishini takomillashtirish bo'yicha takliflar berildi.

ANALYSIS OF REHABILITATION SERVICE AND NURSING ACTIVITY AT BOARDING HOUSE FOR DISABLED CHILDREN

Key words: disabled children, boarding school, rehabilitation, nurse, work.

Abstract: Analysis of the impact of the rehabilitation program at the boarding school for children with disabilities, studying the social significance of the nursing of the boarding school and the factors affecting it, expert assessment of the work of the nurse, the lifestyle of children under medical and social services in the institution (n-451), health indicators, medical history were studied. The quality of medical care of

the nurses (52), the level of use of medical equipment and technologies were analyzed. Conclusions on research results of the study and proposals on improving nursing are given.

АНАЛИЗ РАБОТЫ МЕДСЕСТРЫ ПО УХОДУ ЗА ДЕТЬМИ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ

Ключевые слова: дети-инвалиды, дом-интернат, реабилитация, медсестра, работа.

Аннотация: Уровневый анализ воздействия реабилитационной программы в школе-интернате для детей-инвалидов, изучение социальной значимости работы медицинской сестры интерната и факторов, влияющих на нее, экспертная оценка работы медицинской сестры, детей на медико-социальном службе в учреждении (n-451) изучались образ жизни, показатели здоровья, история болезни. Медсестры (52) проанализировали качество оказания медицинской помощи, уровень использования медицинского оборудования и технологий. Даны выводы по результатам исследования и предложения по улучшению сестринского ухода.

Relevance: Article 25 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) affirms the right of persons with disabilities to the highest attainable standard of health without discrimination. Children with disabilities often require special rehabilitation services related to their disability or limited activity. The biggest obstacles they face are negative attitudes [8 p 1]. All of these factors make disability high on the child and adolescent health agenda. Rehabilitation services should be expanded to include all children in need. Countries must commit to giving priority to the most disadvantaged children in society[2 p 73]. As the number of mental illnesses in the world increases, the problems associated with the mental health of the population become more urgent. A person suffering from a lifelong mental illness needs psychosocial support. The very term "psychosocial" refers to the interaction of various units of the mental health care system and the system of social protection of the population. The main goal of working with the mentally ill is not isolating them from society within the walls of psychiatric hospitals and neuropsychiatric boarding schools, but comprehensive rehabilitation and creating conditions for the full functioning of

patients in society [1 p 56]. Children of specialized boarding schools are under constant medical supervision, as they have certain developmental disabilities, so medical supervision of their general health is important. By analyzing the individual cards of children, taking into account their place of residence, gender and age, it is possible to trace the dynamics of morbidity by the same value. When developing materials on childhood diseases, a list of classes and names of diseases according to ICD-10 was used. After statistical processing of a number of indicators at this stage of the study, we were able to give a detailed description of the incidence of children in individual schools, in the years of observation, depending on the sex and age of children [7 p 110].

The main task of the nurse is the medical rehabilitation of the disabled, the appointment of medication (on the recommendation of a doctor) treatment, therapeutic injections, dressings and emergency medical care, pharmacological therapy, organization of health and rehabilitation activities: exercise therapy, hydrotherapy, massage, physiotherapy exercises, prevention of infectious and socially significant diseases [6 p 17].

In the implementation of individual rehabilitation of a disabled child, the sequence, complexity and continuity of the implementation of rehabilitation or rehabilitation measures, dynamic monitoring and control over the effectiveness of the measures taken are ensured. The boarding institution sends an extract from the individual rehabilitation of a disabled person to the executive authority in the relevant field of activity of the subject, to the territorial divisions of the Social Insurance Fund at the place of residence of the disabled child; determined by those who carry out rehabilitation or rehabilitation activities in accordance with his individual rehabilitation [3 p 240]. The rehabilitation specialist and the rehabilitation nurse work together. After active rehabilitation measures, it was found that about 80% of people with a diagnosis of "childhood disability" were able to get a job in the future and earn a living on their own. It should not be forgotten that the social prognosis is relatively positive in mild mental retardation.

Modern research shows that the number of children with partial developmental disabilities is increasing. Studies provide information about 5-15% of children (mentally retarded). It should be noted that various endogenous and exogenous factors affecting the continuous growth of this category of children should be taken into account by medical personnel [4p 68, 5 p 139]

The law is also aimed at protecting the rights of persons undergoing treatment for mental and neurological diseases, including the rights of children being treated in State institutions or long-term care institutions, as well as the right to receive free medical and legal assistance. Legal foundations have been created for the greatest integration of medical services into primary health care, strengthening the human rights of people suffering from mental and neurological diseases [9] In some medical institutions, the information system is still maintained mainly on paper. In order to promote e-health, efforts have been launched to introduce e-health programs. State primary health care clinics will be launched in a test mode, and in the next stages it is planned that all medical institutions will switch to an electronic system [10].

Material and methods. Children with disabilities (n-451), working nurses (52), medical care provided by nurses in the institution of medical and social services in Tashkent, multi-stage random sampling methods (cluster, expert) have been used.

Results. The average age of nurses was 34,1 years. When calculating seniority at the workplace, work experience in years showed an average of 6,6 years. According to qualification category, 37,5% of nurses have no category, 30% of nurses have 2nd category, 30% have the 1st category, 0,5% have the highest category. What will you personally gain from the training? 27,5% of nurses answered the question that it was an increase in income, 72% was an increase in their professional position, and 0,5% was the respect of their colleagues. 35% of nurses work at night and 65% of them day time. Working hours of morning nurses are from 09:00 to 15:30. Day nurses work from 15:30 to 09:00. To the question, do

you want to study in the future? 45% of nurses were positive, 35% were negative, and 20% of nurses expressed their desire to study if possible. It can be seen that nurses who want to continuously develop their knowledge have a high desire to learn. 68,5% of nurses are satisfied with their work, 27,5% like their work very much, 2,5% of nurses answered that they are not satisfied sometimes [Pic.1].

1-Picture. The level of satisfaction with the work of a nurse

During her work, the nurse must constantly monitor and rehabilitate disabled children assigned to her, perform many other tasks and keep documents correctly. The nurse should be more involved in the care of children with disabilities. We noticed that all the nurses' documents are still in paper form. Knowing that all documents are that provide information about nursing, we also found duplicate documents among them. Apparently, this leads to overspending and less time for the caring of children. In order to improve the efficiency of the use of new technologies in the work process, 20% of nurses are satisfied with the provision of computers in their workplaces, while 80% of nurses do not have computers and tablets [Pic.2].

2-picture. Necessary conditions for the nurse for working in the electronic medical system

Also, the time spent on recording doctor's recommendations and drawing up documents was 2 hours 25 minutes (23,3%) of the total time. Of course, the use of modern technologies and innovations in the activity facilitates the work of a nurse.

A rehabilitation nurse conducts a rehabilitation course for children only with a doctor's recommendation. That is she deals with each child individually. The work of a ward nurse is somewhat complicated and she is obliged to constantly monitor the health of the children attached to her. 3 hours and 10 minutes of nurses' work (26,9%) are spent on administering injections, monitoring children's lunches, monitoring daytime sleep, and sanitary and educational work.

Boarding school children are under the constant supervision of a doctor and in addition, twice a year, they undergo an in-depth medical examination. All information describing children's health status is included in individual cards (f. 025 / u). According to the results of the in-depth medical examination conducted in 2020, 94,9% of the total number of children (451) were disabled congenital anomalies, of which 53,3% (268) were boys, 46,6 percent (183) are girls. (Table 1).

Table 1

Structural indicators of children's house 2020

Including:	Total number of children	Girls	Boys
Total	451	183	268
Walking children	239	85	154
Crawling children	97	52	45
Bedridden children	115	69	46

Among comorbidities, diseases of the nervous system (12,4%), anemia (11,9%) and coronary heart disease were noted with high rates. This is followed by diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (4,6%) and upper respiratory tract (ENT) (3,9%), endocrine diseases (1,3%). Most of these diseases occur in bedridden children, which prompts further development of rehabilitation courses for them (Pic. 3).

Picture 3. Daily medical monitoring of bedridden children

In addition, we got acquainted with the equipment intended for bedridden children in rehabilitation rooms and made sure that there are no special devices that bring the child into a vertical position in bed. It was found that nanny and nurse face several inconveniences in bed child care. Below is a picture of a wheelchair used in the boarding area. We made sure that all beds are used in prams (Pic.4).

Picture 4. Wheelchairs in a boarding school

Conclusion. According to the qualification category (category), 37,5% of nurses do not have a category, 30% of nurses have the 2nd category, 30% of nurses have the 1st category, 0,5% of nurses have the highest category. A number of shortcomings in the ongoing social and medical activities, rehabilitation work and evaluation of the work of nursing staff have been identified. For example, bureaucracy that hinders the implementation of social and medical work (30%), lack of computers in the workplace (80%), waiting in line for rehabilitation, rehabilitation courses stuck in old programs, the need to update methods of working with disabled children, innovative equipment can be brought shortcomings in the material and technical base, lack of qualified specialists, etc.

Recommendation. Based on the existing problems, it is necessary

to organize lecture or seminars in order to increase the level of knowledge and skills of nurses on the basis of a modern rehabilitation program system, and transfer their documents to an electronic system.

To create a rehabilitation modern technical tool (upright stroller) for children with disabilities, contributing to the preservation of their health and for social support of children with developmental disabilities and in need of treatment and rehabilitation, their education, outdoor walks and recreation. In order to optimize the adaptive environment, research is being conducted on the creation of a new type of wheelchair for bedridden and disabled children on the basis of a state grant. In the next steps, we recommend commissioning the wheelchair and conducting research.

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